

The Chaos of Speaking: How Do Learners Adapt to Spontaneous Speech Challenges?

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Abstract: Spontaneous speech presents a significant challenge for EFL learners, requiring them to process and produce language in real time while managing cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social demands. This study explored how university students prepare and enhance their spontaneous speaking. A mixed-method approach was used for the study; 313 students completed a questionnaire, and 30 students participated in semi-structured interviews. The quantitative study results revealed that students prefer to use cognitive strategies such as mental rehearsal and metacognitive awareness, linguistic strategies such as paraphrasing and discourse markers, psychological strategies such as self-efficacy and anxiety regulation, and social strategies like peer learning and role-play. The qualitative findings also depict how learners apply and understand these strategies in real-time speaking situations and how they affect communication. These results agree with previous research, which has also highlighted the role of strategy in spontaneous speech.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Anlık konuşma
Bilişsel stratejiler
Dilsel stratejiler
Psikolojik stratejiler
Toplumsal stratejiler

Konuşmanın Kaosu: Öğrenciler Anlık Konuşma Zorluklarına Nasıl Uyum Sağlar?

Özet: Anlık konuşma, İngilizceyi yabancı dil olarak öğrenenler için önemli bir güçlük oluşturmaktadır. Bu süreç, öğrencilerin dili gerçek zamanlı olarak işlemelerini ve üretmelerini gerektirdiği gibi aynı zamanda bilişsel, dilsel, psikolojik ve toplumsal taleplerle başa çıkmalarını da zorunlu kılmaktadır. Bu çalışma, üniversite öğrencilerinin anlık konuşmaya nasıl hazırlandıklarını ve bu beceriyi nasıl geliştirdiklerini incelemektedir. Çalışmada karma yöntem kullanılmıştır. Nicel veriler 313 öğrencinin doldurmuş olduğu bir anket ile toplanırken, nitel veriler 30 öğrenci ile yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmelerden elde edilmiştir. Nicel bulgular, öğrencilerin bilişsel stratejileri (ör. zihinsel prova ve üstbilişsel farkındalık), dilsel stratejileri (ör. yeniden ifade etme ve söylem belirteçleri), psikolojik stratejileri (ör. öz yeterlik ve kaygı düzenleme) ve toplumsal stratejileri (ör. akran öğrenmesi ve rol yapma) kullanmayı tercih ettiklerini ortaya koymuştur. Nitel bulgular ise öğrencilerin bu stratejileri gerçek zamanlı konuşma durumlarında nasıl uyguladıklarını ve kavradıklarını, ayrıca bu stratejilerin iletişime nasıl etki ettiğini göstermektedir. Bu sonuçlar, anlık konuşmada stratejilerin rolünü vurgulayan önceki araştırmalarla da örtüşmektedir.

1. Introduction

Spontaneous speech is one of the most challenging aspects of second language learning; learners have to organize and express language in real time while being aware of many cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social aspects. Since spontaneous speech is not rehearsed, there is limited time for planning and editing, making it an important area of study for EFL learning. Many learners face difficulties in fluency, hesitation, lexical retrieval, and anxiety when participating in live interactions. As a result, knowing how learners cope with these requirements is crucial to designing suitable educational strategies that can help them communicate more spontaneously. Learners' self-assessment of their oral abilities is equally important for tailoring instruction, as Dunifa (2023) found when evaluating non-English majors' needs in speaking programs. Research has analyzed spontaneous speech creation alongside student strategies for addressing production challenges, but a thorough understanding remains elusive. Research explains that spontaneous speech production creates significant cognitive strain on learners as they perform vocabulary retrieval and develop sentence structure and real-time output monitoring (Choe, 2020). Research explains that linguistic strategies, including paraphrasing and discourse markers, help learners maintain fluency while navigating vocabulary challenges (Saito & Plonsky, 2019). Self-efficacy and anxiety control represent the psychological variables that directly impact students' willingness to participate in spontaneous oral activities, according to Nissen (2023).

Wilschut et al. (2021) show interactive speaking practice and peer collaboration as social strategies that enhance adaptability and communicative competence. A comprehensive understanding of how learners fuse multiple adaptation strategies to address spontaneous speaking challenges remains absent, although research continues to expand. The study aims to explore the following four aspects of adaptation strategies that EFL learners employ in spontaneous speech: Cognitive strategies, such as mental rehearsal, scaffolding, and metacognitive awareness; Linguistic strategies, such as paraphrasing, discourse markers, and simplification; Psychological strategies, such as self-efficacy, anxiety regulation, and positive self-talk; and Social strategies such as peer learning, active listening, and role-play. Through both quantitative and qualitative approaches, the study offers an in-depth understanding of learners' adaptive behaviors and the efficacy of these strategies in enhancing spontaneous speaking ability.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Spontaneous Speaking

Spontaneous speech, which is unplanned and produced in real-time, requires the speaker to think and speak at the same time, which results in pauses, repetitions, and corrections (Saleem, 2023; Wang et al., 2018). Despite being unpredictable, spontaneous speech is important in language learning as it shows how well a learner can use language in real-life situations (Myhre & Fiskum, 2020; Park, 2024). L2 fluency goes beyond making mistakes; it is the ability to use language effectively and to participate in discussions frequently required in academic and workplace settings (Efrizah, 2024; Jiang et al., 2022). This paper has argued that through spontaneous speaking tasks, the frequency of speaking is increased and, in turn, improves fluency (McDonough & Sato, 2019).

The spontaneity effect manifested through hesitations, false starts, and self-corrections is not only a problem but also reveals cognitive processes involved in language production. For instance, hesitation can be seen as a cognitive tool that helps the speakers moderate the discourse sequence (Baqué & Machuca, 2023). However, time pressure increases these

disfluencies as the learners must try to balance fluency and accuracy (Zhu et al., 2017). This is because of the unpredictability of spontaneous speech (Myhre & Fiskum, 2020; Yıldız, 2024). These challenges demand a cognitive, linguistic, and psychological solution. Cognitive adaptation deals with high levels of disfluency, like lexical retrieval failures, self-repairs, fillers, and repetitions, which are indicators of the cognitive complexity of spontaneous speech (Choe, 2020). Linguistic strategies such as explicit pronunciation instruction can help L2 learners to improve their phonetic awareness and, thus, their spontaneous speech production (Saito et al., 2019). Anxiety and task-related pressures are vast predictors of learners' performance; thus, supporting learning environments is needed to build confidence in learners (Nissen, 2023).

Flexibility in speech production is important for communication because the learners' strategies vary according to the situation (Fraser, 2023). Current technological tools, such as speech recognition tools, are useful in providing instantaneous feedback to learners on their mistakes and ways to improve their speaking strategies (Wilschut et al., 2021). Technology in language learning can be described as an interactive adaptation that helps students develop spontaneous speech within a controlled and dynamic environment. Therefore, based on the findings of the current review, it can be concluded that spontaneous speech is an essential component of language proficiency; however, it entails certain cognitive, linguistic, and psychological challenges. Hence, by deploying strategic adaptations, more frequent practice, and using technology, the learner should be better positioned to improve their fluency and confidence in real-time communication.

2.2. Theoretical Foundations of Spontaneous Speaking

2.2.1. Complexity and Dynamic Systems Theory

The complexity and dynamic systems theory (Larsen-Freeman, 1997) is applied to spontaneous speech, where language learning and production are seen as non-deterministic and adaptive. Nonlinearity is key; language use is not just rule application (Kuznetsov & Slepneva, 2020). Speakers tailor their speech based on feedback, context, and cognition, especially in spontaneous dialogue (Xie & Antolovic, 2021). Almost all minor cognitive or environmental changes can significantly change speech (Alexandrou et al., 2018). Errors and pauses are manifestations of the cognitive processes that underpin speech (Janse, 2004); time pressure boosts disfluencies (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014). Chaos in spontaneous speech reveals fluency problems (Borrie & Liss, 2014).

2.2.2. Levelt's Model of Speech Production

Levelt's (1989) Model of Speech Production provides a structured framework for understanding the cognitive processes involved in spontaneous speaking. This model delineates three primary stages: conceptualization, formulation, and articulation, each of which plays a critical role in producing spontaneous speech. Conceptualization: Speakers generate ideas based on knowledge, experience, and context, selecting relevant information for expression (Kieft & Nearey, 2013). This stage is challenging in spontaneous speech due to the lack of pre-planning. Formulation: Ideas are structured into linguistic forms, requiring word choice, grammar, and sentence construction. High cognitive load often leads to pauses, corrections, and disfluencies (Chen et al., 2009; Nasrolahzadeh et al., 2018). Articulation: The last stage is the articulation stage, in which the formulated message is produced. This stage encompasses the motor functions needed for speech production, including the movement of the vocal organs. Articulation can be affected by various factors, including the speaker's emotional state, level of anxiety, and degree of familiarity with the subject matter.

Disfluencies often accompany spontaneous speaking as speakers are pressured to produce language quickly. Thus, they may encounter difficulties maintaining a fluent speech rate while engaging in the required cognitive processes (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014). Speaking spontaneously is a process that occurs concurrently with the context of conversation. This means speakers always solve cognitive limitations and unpredictability, showing language use's generative and incremental nature (based on Merz et al., 2022; Murao & Ito, 2015). These include complexity and dynamic systems theory, as well as Levelt's speech production model, which depicts spontaneous speaking as nonlinear and adaptive. These frameworks are understood to help educators design more successful learning strategies so that learners can learn to handle the real-time communication challenges they will face.

2.3. Common Challenges in Spontaneous Speaking

Spontaneous speaking presents many challenges that can be categorized into cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and sociolinguistic factors. Each category encompasses difficulties learners face when communicating in real time, often under pressure.

2.3.1. Cognitive Challenges

This paper finds that spontaneous speaking entails retrieving linguistic information, organizing thoughts, and forming responses online, which are accompanied by pauses and errors (Lobanova et al., 2022). Translating thoughts from the mother tongue into English can make for incoherent speech, and cognitive overload may cause anxiety, further hindering fluency (Zhu & Zhou, 2012). The difficulty is increased by the number of cognitive tasks that must be performed simultaneously, such as listening and planning while speaking, particularly for learners with language disabilities (Bedore & Leonard, 2005; Murao & Ito, 2015).

2.3.2. Linguistics challenges

Kassem's (2018) and Madzlan et al.'s (2020) research highlights that learners face limited vocabulary, grammatical errors, and pronunciation issues that may affect communication. The pressure of spontaneous speech only worsens these issues, resulting in disfluencies and repetitive structures. Thus, vocabulary and grammatical accuracy need to be expanded to enhance fluency.

2.3.3. Psychological and affective factors

Anxiety can make learners avoid speaking activities altogether, leading to doubts and frustration about themselves (Fathikasari et al., 2022; Zhu & Zhou, 2012). Other factors, like the fear of making mistakes and peer evaluation, also limit participation. One way to encourage a safe and supportive environment is by using improvisation games, which can help build students' confidence (Zondag, 2021).

2.3.4. Sociolinguistic challenges

Cultural norms, language patterns, and the influence of one's mother tongue all shape the way people speak spontaneously. The main challenge of code-switching is linguistic interference, which may result in errors and reduced fluency (Efrizah, 2024; Younes & Albalawi, 2016). Pragmatic aspects, such as refusals and other speech acts, also influence spontaneous interactions, as shown in Khamkhien's (2022) study of Thai L2 learners. Dialect, age, and gender also affect articulation and speech perception (Jacewicz et al., 2009). In conclusion, spontaneous speaking presents various challenges that learners must navigate, including

cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and sociolinguistic factors. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach incorporating targeted practice, supportive learning environments, and an understanding of the social dynamics of language use. By recognizing and addressing these challenges, educators can better support learners in developing spontaneous speaking skills and enhancing their overall language proficiency.

2.4. How Learners Adapt to Spontaneous Speech Challenges

Spontaneous speech is a crucial skill that learners must develop to communicate effectively, but it is accompanied by myriad problems that can prevent them from doing so effectively. To this end, learners employ several coping mechanisms to work around these problems effectively. To navigate these challenges, learners employ various adaptive strategies across cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and interactive dimensions to improve their spontaneous speaking skills.

2.4.1. Cognitive adaptation

Cognitive adaptation theory is the study of how learners cope with spontaneous speaking. A key strategy is scaffolding, where learners try to express their ideas simply before they can verbalize them, helping to organize their thoughts and decrease cognitive load, especially in high-risk tasks (Akkakoson, 2016). Chunking, the division of speech into smaller, meaningful parts, enhances fluency and prevents hesitation (Mathuranath et al., 2004). Mental rehearsal, learners' conversation simulation, enhances their fluency and readies them for potential issues (Xie & Antolovic, 2021). Also, metacognitive awareness enables learners to identify their abilities and deficiencies and plan to practice specific aspects of the learning process, such as vocabulary or accuracy (Nip & Green, 2013). These strategies enable learners to manage the process of speaking development and view problems as opportunities for growth.

2.4.2. Linguistic strategies

Strategies are tools that learners use to orient themselves in the complexity of spontaneous speech. A typical strategy is paraphrasing, which involves restating one's ideas using different words or structures when a learner lacks the appropriate vocabulary to express a particular idea. This strategy helps maintain the conversation's continuity and demonstrates the learner's linguistic flexibility (Nugroho & Atmojo, 2022). However, an equally effective linguistic strategy uses fillers or discourse markers such as *um*, *you know*, or *well*. Although they may seem like mere hesitations, they serve a purpose in that they provide the learners with a way to pause while still carrying on the conversation with their interlocutors (Velayudhan et al., 2014). This technique can help reduce anxiety and pressure, allowing learners to concentrate on forming their responses. Furthermore, learners may employ a strategic simplification strategy, deliberately choosing more basic vocabulary and sentence structures to express themselves. This approach may enhance comprehension and reduce errors, especially in high-stakes speaking tasks (Young, 2024). In this way, learners can focus on the effectiveness of communication rather than the complexity of the language, gaining confidence in expressing themselves at length as they transition from planned to spontaneous speech.

2.4.3. Psychological adaptation

Psychological adaptation includes how speakers manage the stress and anxiety that comes with spontaneous speaking. A key point on the issue of psychological adaptation is the idea of *self-efficacy*, which is the individual's belief in his or her potential to succeed in certain positions.

Learners with high *self-efficacy* will likely come to spontaneous speaking situations with courage, looking at the difficulties as obstacles that can be easily removed (Zheng & Cheng, 2018). For example, learners may use *positive self-talk* when deliberately trying to replace negative thoughts with kind words about their capabilities. Instead of thinking, “I will mess up,” learners might tell themselves, “I have prepared for this, and I can express my ideas.” This change in attitude can significantly affect anxiety and performance when speaking spontaneously (Puluhulawa et al., 2022). Furthermore, learners may stand to gain from *exposure therapy*, a psychological method that includes working through anxiety-producing situations. Engaging in low-risk speaking activities, such as small group discussions with other learners or simulation of a speech before a mirror, can ease the fear of spontaneous speaking (Lasprilla et al., 2022). It is possible to desensitize the patient to the fear through gradual exposure to increased levels of anxiety in speaking (Çakmak, 2022).

Moreover, cultivating a *growth mindset*—the belief that abilities can be developed through effort and learning—can empower learners to embrace challenges and view setbacks as opportunities for growth. This mindset encourages resilience and persistence, essential qualities for navigating the ups and downs of spontaneous speaking (Keshree et al., 2013). Furthermore, implementing a growth mindset, the perception that abilities can be developed through effort and learning, can enable learners to confront challenges and consider setbacks as learning opportunities. This mindset develops tenacity and perseverance, critical qualities one needs to navigate the highs and lows of spontaneous speaking (Keshree et al., 2013).

2.4.4. *Interactive and social adaptation*

Spontaneous speaking learners’ strategies refer to how they engage in social processes during the speaking process. Effective communication involves lexical resources, non-verbal cues, turn-taking, and conversational rules. One effective strategy is the acquisition of *active listening skills*, which helps learners participate effectively in conversations. This way, learners can listen to what others are saying and develop appropriate responses to feed into the conversation (Custodio et al., 2020). Furthermore, learners can play *role-play or simulation games* to improve their social compatibility. These activities help learners try out different situations in real-life conversations, thus making them more confident in various speaking situations and interactions (René et al., 2023). It is also possible that through role-playing, learners can get feedback on their communication patterns and how they approach spontaneous speaking. Besides, learners can benefit from developing a social network of friends and tutors who help and guide them in learning the language. Group discussions, language exchanges, or conversation clubs will give learners plenty of chances to speak spontaneously in a safe environment, creating a community of learners (Saito et al., 2006).

3. Method

3.1. Research Design

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating quantitative and qualitative data to explore how EFL learners adapt to spontaneous speech challenges. A questionnaire gathers large-scale data on learners’ adaptation strategies, while semi-structured interviews provide deeper insights into individual experiences.

3.2. Participants

This research includes 313 undergraduate students of EFL universities in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. Participants were chosen through stratified random sampling to include participants

from all levels of proficiency, academic backgrounds, and genders. Most students are English majors (63.3%), and the rest, 36.7%, are from other fields where English is a prerequisite. All the participants have been exposed to English for at least six years and are currently enrolled in speaking-focused EFL courses. The sample has 44.7% of the students at B1, which is an intermediate level of fluency on the CEFR scale. Furthermore, 30 students are chosen for semi-structured interviews to learn more about their strategies for adapting to spontaneous speech challenges. Table 1 shows the demographic breakdown of the participants.

Table 1.
Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic variable	Category	Number	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	125	40
	Female	188	60
Age	18-19 years	85	27.2
	20-21 years	145	46.3
	Over 21 years	83	26.5
English proficiency	A2 (Basic Users)	102	32.6
	B1 (Intermediate Users)	140	44.7
	B2 (Upper-Intermediate Users)	71	22.7
Academic background	English Majors	198	63.3
	Non-English Majors	115	36.7

3.3. Instrumentation

This study employs a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews to examine how EFL learners adapt to spontaneous speech challenges through cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social strategies. The questionnaire, administered to 313 university students, assesses key strategies such as scaffolding (Akkakoson, 2016), chunking (Mathuranath et al., 2004), and mental rehearsal (Xie & Antolovic, 2021) for cognitive adaptation. Linguistic strategies include paraphrasing (Nugroho & Atmojo, 2022), discourse markers (Velayudhan et al., 2014), and strategic simplification (Young, 2024). Psychological adaptation focuses on self-efficacy (Zheng & Cheng, 2018), positive self-talk (Puluhulawa et al., 2022), exposure-based practice (Lasprilla et al., 2022), and growth mindset (Keshree et al., 2013). Social strategies cover active listening (Custodio et al., 2020), role-play (René et al., 2023), and peer-based learning (Saito et al., 2006), as shown in Table 2. Additionally, semi-structured interviews with 30 participants provide qualitative insights, with responses analyzed thematically, while questionnaire data is processed using SPSS to identify adaptation patterns.

Table 2.
Description of the questionnaire

Clusters	No. of items	Sample	Source
Cognitive strategies	05	I break long sentences into smaller chunks to improve fluency.	Xie & Antolovic (2021)
Linguistic strategies	05	I simplify my vocabulary when I cannot recall complex words.	Young (2024)
Psychological strategies	05	I practice speaking in front of a mirror or recording myself.	Lasprilla et al. (2022)
Social strategies	05	I participate in group discussions to practice spontaneous speaking.	René et al. (2023)

Note. The table does not include all items. Instead, only one item from each cluster is presented as a reference.

3.4. Data Collection

This research uses a self-administered questionnaire and semi-structured interviews to explore how EFL learners cope with spontaneous speech. The self-administered questionnaire used to determine cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social adaptation strategies was completed by 313 university students from the Mekong Delta. It took participants about 15-20 minutes to complete the questionnaire, either directly from the researcher or through an online survey. The responses were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, where one is Strongly Disagree, and five is Strongly Agree. To ensure the instrument's reliability, the questionnaire was first trialed on several students, and changes were made based on their feedback. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted with 30 participants better to understand learners' real-life experiences of spontaneous speech adaptation. The interviews were conducted in person or via Zoom, and all interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed, and analyzed thematically.

3.5. Data Analysis

In the data analysis process, participants' responses to the questionnaire were analyzed using SPSS for descriptive (e.g., mean scores, standard deviations, etc.) and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics provided an overall numeric understanding of how participants follow cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social adaptation strategies in spontaneous speech. Additionally, qualitative data from semi-structured interviews were transcribed verbatim and thematically analyzed using MaxQDA. These qualitative data were categorized and analyzed iteratively to generate themes and subthemes related to participants' adoption strategies (e.g., cognitive processing, linguistic flexibility, anxiety management, and social engagement). In this way, qualitative data supported the quantitative findings.

4. Findings

4.1. Quantitative Results

4.1.1. Cognitive strategies

The results indicate that learners actively employ cognitive strategies to manage spontaneous speech challenges.

Table 3.

Descriptive Statistics of Learners' Cognitive Strategies in Spontaneous Speech

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. I mentally rehearse what I am about to say before speaking.	313	3.91	0.87
2. I break long sentences into smaller chunks to improve fluency.	313	4.02	0.79
3. I monitor and reflect on my speaking performance to improve.	313	3.76	0.91
4. I simplify my ideas before verbalizing them.	313	3.89	0.85
5. I focus on the key points of my message to avoid getting lost.	313	4.11	0.76
6. I use previously learned expressions or set phrases to respond quickly.	313	3.94	0.83
7. I visualize possible conversations before engaging in spontaneous speech.	313	3.61	0.96
8. I train myself to think in English rather than translating from my first language.	313	3.45	1.02
9. I predict possible responses from my conversation partner.	313	3.72	0.88
10. I try to stay aware of my speaking habits and correct them over time.	313	3.85	0.91

Among these strategies, the most frequently used was focusing on key points to avoid getting lost ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.76$), suggesting that learners prioritize structuring their speech for clarity. Breaking long sentences into smaller chunks to improve fluency ($M = 4.02$, $SD =$

0.79) was also commonly employed, reflecting the effectiveness of chunking in facilitating smoother speech production. Additionally, using previously learned expressions or set phrases to respond quickly ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.83$) and mentally rehearsing speech before speaking ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.87$) highlight learners' reliance on pre-planned structures to manage real-time speaking challenges. Simplifying ideas before verbalizing ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.85$) and staying aware of speaking habits to correct them over time ($M = 3.85$, $SD = 0.91$) further emphasize learners' metacognitive awareness in improving their speech performance.

Conversely, the least frequently used cognitive strategy was training oneself to think in English rather than translating from the first language ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 1.02$), indicating that many learners still depend on their native language for speech processing. Visualizing possible conversations before speaking ($M = 3.61$, $SD = 0.96$) and predicting responses from conversation partners ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.88$) also showed moderate use, suggesting that not all learners actively engage in predictive cognitive strategies. The findings suggest that learners prioritize fluency-enhancing techniques, such as focusing on key points, chunking, and utilizing pre-learned expressions. However, strategies that promote spontaneous speech production, such as thinking in English and visualizing conversations in advance, still need improvement. These insights can inform targeted instructional strategies further to develop learners' cognitive adaptability in spontaneous speaking tasks.

4.1.2. Linguistic adaptation strategies

The results indicate that learners actively employ various linguistic strategies to maintain fluency and clarity in spontaneous speech.

Table 4.

Descriptive Statistics of Learners' Linguistic Strategies in Spontaneous Speech

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
11. I paraphrase when I do not know the exact word.	313	4.08	0.74
12. I use discourse markers like 'well,' 'you know,' or 'actually' to maintain fluency.	313	3.92	0.80
13. I simplify my vocabulary when I cannot recall complex words.	313	4.01	0.79
14. I consciously use synonyms to keep the conversation going.	313	3.89	0.85
15. I use fillers like "um" or "uh" to buy time while thinking.	313	3.65	0.92
16. I adjust my speech rate depending on the complexity of my thoughts.	313	3.98	0.83
17. I use gestures and facial expressions to support my spoken message.	313	4.12	0.75
18. I pay attention to stress and intonation to convey meaning clearly.	313	3.91	0.87
19. I repeat or rephrase my statements to ensure I am understood.	313	4.05	0.81
20. I ask my conversation partner to repeat or clarify if I do not understand.	313	4.15	0.74

The most frequently used strategy was asking conversation partners to repeat or clarify when something was not understood ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.74$), highlighting the importance of interactive adjustments in ensuring communication effectiveness. Similarly, using gestures and facial expressions to support spoken messages ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.75$) was highly rated, emphasizing learners' reliance on non-verbal cues to aid comprehension. Paraphrasing when the exact word is unknown ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.74$) and repeating or rephrasing statements to ensure understanding ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.81$) were also commonly employed, suggesting that learners prioritize maintaining communication flow despite lexical gaps. Simplifying vocabulary when complex words are difficult to recall ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.79$) and adjusting speech rate depending on the complexity of thoughts ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.83$) further illustrate learners' adaptability in managing speech production constraints. Conversely, strategies such as using fillers like "um" or "uh" to buy time while thinking ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 0.92$) were among the

least frequently used, suggesting that while learners may occasionally rely on hesitation markers, they generally strive for fluency through more structured linguistic strategies. Using discourse markers like “well,” “you know,” or “actually” ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.80$) and paying attention to stress and intonation for more precise meaning ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.87$) were moderately employed, indicating an awareness of conversational coherence and pronunciation dynamics. The findings suggest that learners actively utilize linguistic strategies to manage lexical challenges and enhance spoken communication. While paraphrasing, rephrasing, and non-verbal cues are widely used, increased focus on prosodic features such as intonation and strategic use of fillers could further improve their spontaneous speaking skills.

4.1.3. Psychological strategies

The results demonstrate that learners employ various psychological strategies to manage anxiety and build confidence in spontaneous speech.

Table 5.

Descriptive Statistics of Learners’ Psychological Strategies in Spontaneous Speech

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
21. I replace negative thoughts with encouraging self-talk.	313	3.72	0.90
22. I take risks and speak even when unsure of my grammar.	313	3.58	1.01
23. I practice speaking in front of a mirror or recording myself.	313	3.49	1.05
24. I remind myself that making mistakes is part of learning.	313	4.13	0.76
25. I focus on the meaning of my message rather than worrying about mistakes.	313	3.95	0.83
26. I engage in relaxation techniques (e.g., deep breathing) to reduce speaking anxiety.	313	3.62	0.94
27. I seek feedback on my speaking skills and use it to improve.	313	4.07	0.78
28. I try to maintain a positive attitude toward spontaneous speaking.	313	4.19	0.73
29. I recall past successful speaking experiences to boost confidence.	313	3.84	0.88
30. I set small, achievable speaking goals to track my progress.	313	3.98	0.79

The most frequently used strategy was maintaining a positive attitude towards spontaneous speaking ($M = 4.19$, $SD = 0.73$), indicating that learners recognize the role of mindset in overcoming communication challenges. Similarly, reminding themselves that making mistakes is part of learning ($M = 4.13$, $SD = 0.76$) and seeking feedback to improve speaking skills ($M = 4.07$, $SD = 0.78$) were highly rated, suggesting that learners actively adopt constructive approaches to self-improvement. Learners also reported setting small, achievable speaking goals to track progress ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.79$) and focusing on the meaning of their message rather than worrying about mistakes ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.83$) as effective strategies in spontaneous speech adaptation. Recalling past successful speaking experiences to boost confidence ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.88$) and using encouraging self-talk ($M = 3.72$, $SD = 0.90$) were also moderately utilized, indicating an awareness of the importance of self-motivation. Conversely, practicing in front of a mirror or recording oneself ($M = 3.49$, $SD = 1.05$) and taking risks by speaking even when unsure of grammar ($M = 3.58$, $SD = 1.01$) were among the least frequently used strategies. This suggests that while learners recognize the importance of psychological preparation, they may hesitate to engage in more direct self-exposure practices. Additionally, relaxation techniques such as deep breathing to reduce speaking anxiety ($M = 3.62$, $SD = 0.94$) had a relatively lower mean, indicating that learners may rely more on cognitive and linguistic strategies than stress-management techniques. Overall, the findings suggest that learners adopt a positive and reflective approach to spontaneous speech but could benefit from increased risk-taking behaviors and self-exposure practices to build confidence and fluency in high-pressure speaking situations.

4.1.4. Social strategies

The results indicate that learners actively use various social strategies to enhance their spontaneous speaking skills.

Table 6.

Descriptive Statistics of Learners' Social Strategies in Spontaneous Speech

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
31. I ask for clarification when I do not understand something.	313	4.22	0.72
32. I participate in group discussions to practice spontaneous speaking.	313	3.91	0.86
33. I engage in language exchange or conversation clubs to improve fluency.	313	3.78	0.92
34. I actively listen to my conversational partner before responding.	313	4.26	0.70
35. I use role-play or simulation activities to prepare for real conversations.	313	3.87	0.89
36. I learn from observing how native speakers handle spontaneous speech.	313	4.01	0.81
37. I imitate native speakers' pronunciation and speaking patterns.	313	3.95	0.83
38. I adapt my speaking style depending on my conversation partner.	313	3.86	0.87
39. I practice turn-taking strategies to keep the conversation smooth.	313	4.08	0.75
40. I use humor or small talk to ease into spontaneous conversations.	313	3.79	0.91

The highest-rated strategy was actively listening to the conversation partner before responding ($M = 4.26$, $SD = 0.70$), highlighting the importance of attentiveness in maintaining effective communication. Similarly, asking for clarification when something is not understood ($M = 4.22$, $SD = 0.72$) was highly utilized, reflecting learners' willingness to seek comprehension and maintain conversation flow. Other frequently used strategies included practicing turn-taking to ensure smooth conversations ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.75$) and observing how native speakers handle spontaneous speech ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.81$). Learners also reported imitating native speakers' pronunciation and speaking patterns ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.83$), indicating a conscious effort to refine their spoken English. Social engagement strategies such as participating in group discussions ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.86$), using role-play or simulations ($M = 3.87$, $SD = 0.89$), and adapting speech based on the conversation partner ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.87$) were moderately used, suggesting that learners recognize their benefits but may not always have opportunities to apply them regularly. Conversely, engaging in language exchange or conversation clubs ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.92$) and using humor or small talk to ease into conversations ($M = 3.79$, $SD = 0.91$) were among the least frequently employed strategies. This could indicate that while learners acknowledge the role of informal interactions in improving fluency, they may struggle with confidence or access to such opportunities. The findings suggest that learners rely on active listening, clarification, and observational learning to navigate spontaneous conversations effectively. However, increased participation in conversation clubs and informal interactions could further enhance their ability to adapt to real-world speaking situations.

4.2. Qualitative results

4.2.1. Cognitive strategies

Cognitive strategies play a fundamental role in preparing and organizing spoken output so learners can reduce hesitation and improve fluency during unpredictable conversations. Mental rehearsal was widely reported as a strategy that helps to decrease cognitive overload and increase control over speech production. One participant explained,

Before I open my mouth to speak, I silently rehearse what I will say, thinking about the structure of my sentence, the vocabulary I will use, and how I want my message to come across. This helps me avoid stumbling over my words and gives me a sense of control over my speech. (Participant 3)

Another key strategy was chunking, which helps to split down long pieces of information into more usable and easier-to-manage chunks to help with fluency. A participant explained,

I try to organize my thoughts into small, meaningful groups of words rather than constructing complete sentences on the spot. For example, instead of worrying about forming a long and complicated sentence, I focus on concise phrases that I can connect naturally. This way, I do not feel overwhelmed while speaking. (Participant 12)

This aligns with working memory constraints in language production, as breaking speech into pre-formulated chunks reduces cognitive load and increases fluency. Additionally, anticipatory thinking emerged as an effective technique for enhancing conversational adaptability. One learner described,

Whenever I am conversing, I predict possible follow-up questions or responses from my partner so that I am not caught off guard. I try to have a general idea of what I might say next, which helps me feel more prepared and keeps the conversation flowing naturally. (Participant 18)

In addition, self-monitoring and metacognition or reflective thinking were frequently mentioned, which indicates how learners analyze their performance to refine their speaking strategies over time. One participant shared,

After every conversation, I take a few moments to think about what worked well and what I could have done better. I reflect on whether I hesitated too much, whether my sentences were clear, and if there were words I struggled with. This way, I can work on my weaknesses and feel more confident the next time. (Participant 7)

Finally, a significant cognitive shift occurred when learners stopped translating from their first language and started thinking directly in English. One participant described this transition:

Initially, I used to mentally translate everything from my native language before speaking, which made me very slow and hesitant. However, now, I train myself to think in English, even alone. I describe things around me in English, try to form sentences in my head, and even talk to myself in English. This has really helped me respond faster in conversations without feeling stuck (Participant 30)

Cognitive strategies facilitate speech organization, retrieval efficiency, and adaptive flexibility. Learners who actively engage in mental rehearsal, chunking, anticipatory thinking, and reflective monitoring exhibit greater fluency and confidence in spontaneous speaking.

4.2.2. Linguistic strategies

Students can use linguistic strategies to overcome vocabulary limitations, work around them to maintain coherence, and ensure that their speech sounds organic. A technique that is most commonly employed is paraphrasing, through which speakers can manage lexical gaps without affecting their fluency. A participant elaborated,

I don't stop or panic when I forget a specific word. Instead, I quickly think of a different way to explain the same idea using simpler words. For example, if I can't remember the word 'frustrated,' I might

say 'feeling really upset and annoyed simultaneously.' This keeps the conversation going and makes sure my listener understands me. (Participant 5)

Another essential adaptation was strategic simplification, where learners prioritized clear communication over linguistic complexity. One participant explained,

Instead of using fancy or complicated words, I clarify my message. If I can't recall an advanced word, I immediately switch to a simpler one that conveys the same meaning. I aim to communicate effectively, not impress people with complex vocabulary. (Participant 13)

A notable feature of fluent speakers was their use of discourse markers and fillers to maintain natural rhythm and processing time. One respondent shared,

If I need a second to think, I use phrases like 'well,' 'you know,' or 'let me see...' instead of just staying silent. These little words make my speech sound more natural and help me avoid awkward pauses. (Participant 9)

Another strategy involved intonation and stress modulation to enhance expressiveness and engagement. A participant noted,

I focus on how I say things, not just what I say. If I emphasize keywords and change my tone naturally, my speech sounds more interesting and confident, and people pay more attention (Participant 18)

Finally, speech rate modulation was a crucial self-regulation tool. One learner described,

I slow down when I feel unsure about what to say, but when I am confident, I speed up. This helps me stay in control of my speaking pace and avoid sounding too rushed or too hesitant (Participant 15)

Linguistic strategies can compensate for difficulties and enhance fluency and expressive modulation. Learners who can paraphrase, simplify language, use discourse markers, change intonation, and control speech rate are more coherent and self-assured when engaging in spontaneous conversations.

4.2.3. Psychological strategies

Spontaneous speaking confidence, emotional regulation, and resilience depend heavily on psychological strategies that help learners control their anxieties. The data shows that successful speakers use mindset shifts, anxiety management techniques, and self-affirmation practices to navigate their fears and uncertainties. One of the most frequently mentioned strategies was positive self-talk, where learners replaced self-doubt with encouraging thoughts. A participant reflected,

Whenever I start feeling nervous, I tell myself, 'You've done this before, and you can do it again.' I remind myself that even if I make mistakes, it's not the end of the world. The more I focus on staying positive, the easier it becomes to speak naturally. (Participant 6)

Another widely used approach was desensitization through exposure-based practice, where learners gradually increased their comfort with speaking in real-life scenarios. One participant shared,

At first, I was terrified of speaking in public. But I started by practicing with close friends, then moved on to ordering food in English, and eventually, I participated in class discussions. The more I exposed myself to speaking situations, the less afraid I became. (Participant 14)

Many participants also emphasized the importance of embracing mistakes as part of learning. One respondent stated,

I used to panic whenever I made a grammatical mistake, but now I remind myself that even native speakers don't always speak perfectly. Instead of feeling embarrassed, I focus on learning from my mistakes and improving next time. (Participant 22)

Additionally, relaxation techniques were frequently used to manage physiological symptoms of speaking anxiety. One participant described,

Before speaking, I take a deep breath, slow down my heart rate, and remind myself to relax. If I feel overwhelmed, I pause for a second, collect my thoughts, and then continue speaking. This helps me stay calm and in control. (Participant 27)

Finally, learners boosted their confidence by recalling past successful speaking experiences. One participant explained,

Whenever I feel nervous, I think back to the times when I spoke fluently and was understood. This reminds me that I am capable, and it gives me the motivation to keep going. (Participant 10)

Psychological strategies reduce anxiety, build confidence, and cultivate resilience in spontaneous speaking. Students who practice positive self-talk, incremental step exposure, mistake tolerance, relaxation techniques, and self-affirmation are more emotionally stable and adaptable when participating in real-time conversations.

4.2.4. Social strategies

Through social strategies, learners can navigate conversations effectively by focusing on interactional skills, collaborative learning, and cultural awareness. The data showed that proactive engagement with conversation partners, active listening, and social immersion were important adaptation strategies. One of the most highly valued techniques was active listening, where learners focused on their conversation partner's words to maintain engagement and respond appropriately. A participant emphasized,

I make sure to really listen before I respond, rather than just thinking about what I want to say next. I can respond more naturally and relevantly if I understand the main idea. (Participant 20)

Learners also benefited from peer-based learning, where they practiced spontaneous speaking in supportive group environments. One participant shared,

I join conversation clubs where we talk about different topics every week. Speaking with others helps me get used to different accents, speeds, and styles, which makes real-life conversations easier. (Participant 8)

Another effective strategy was observing and imitating native speakers, which helped learners adapt to natural speech patterns. One participant explained,

I pay attention to how native speakers phrase their sentences, their expressions, and how they react in conversations. Then, I try to copy their style when I speak. (Participant 11)

Role-playing and simulations emerged as powerful tools for preparing learners for diverse speaking situations. A participant stated,

I practice different conversation scenarios with my friends, like ordering at a restaurant or handling a disagreement. This makes me feel more prepared for real interactions because I've already thought about what to say. (Participant 29)

Finally, humor and small talk were used as social lubrication techniques to make conversations more natural and engaging. One learner elaborated,

If I feel nervous, I start with a light joke or a casual comment, like 'Wow, it's so hot today!' This helps me ease into the conversation and makes both my conversation partner and I feel more comfortable. (Participant 17)

Some social strategies can help you improve your conversational skills, be more adaptable, and be culturally sensitive. Learners who can participate in peer discussion, observe native speakers, use humor, role-play, and practice active listening are more likely to develop more interactional fluency and confidence in spontaneous speech.

5. Discussion

This study shows how EFL learners solve the problems of spontaneous speech with the help of cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social strategies. The results are in line with previous studies, which also stress the use of structured cognitive strategies (Choe, 2020), linguistic flexibility (Saito & Plonsky, 2019), psychological resilience (Nissen, 2023), and social interaction (Wilschut et al., 2021). Using quantitative and qualitative data, this discussion examines how these strategies help to facilitate successful real-time communication.

Spontaneous speech is a form of discourse that requires online processing and coherence. Quantitative results show that the learners focus on the key point ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 0.76$) and sentence chunking ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.79$) to maintain fluency. The use of pre-learned expressions ($M = 3.94$, $SD = 0.83$) and mental rehearsal ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.87$) reduces the cognitive load in the process, but several participants still translate what they want to say from their native language ($M = 3.45$, $SD = 1.02$). Qualitative data also affirmed that mental rehearsal reduces hesitation, and speech chunking improves fluency. They self-monitor to fine-tune their approach: "I analyze my performance to improve" (Participant 7). Choe (2020) argued that using cognitive scaffolding techniques decreases disfluencies and increases fluency in spontaneous speech, and these findings support that. Learners use strategies for the control of language in order to deal with the issue of vocabulary size. Quantitative results show that the most frequent strategies are paraphrasing ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.74$), clarification requests ($M = 4.15$, $SD = 0.74$), and gestures ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.75$). The lower use of fillers ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 0.92$) indicates a tendency to avoid more spontaneous speech.

Qualitative responses support these strategies as the participants paraphrased to avoid using a particular word: 'When I forget a word, I try to explain the idea in simpler words' (P5). These results concur with those of Saito and Plonsky (2019), who highlight the significance of explicit strategies for pronunciation and discourse in the development of spontaneous speech. Resilience is a psychological concept that plays an important role in speech adaptation. Quantitative results show that learners with a positive attitude ($M = 4.19$, $SD = .73$) and willingness to accept errors ($M = 4.13$, $SD = .76$) perform better. The desire to

receive feedback ($M = 4.07$, $SD = .78$) and the establishment of small goals ($M = 3.98$, $SD = .79$) help build confidence; however, self-evaluation ($M = 3.49$, $SD = 1.05$) is not as commonly employed. Qualitative responses show that self-regulation helps to reduce anxiety: ‘Thinking too much about grammar makes me hesitate, I should rather concentrate on the message I am trying to convey’ (Participant 22). These findings agree with Nissen (2023), who established that anxiety has a negative effect on pronunciation ratings in spontaneous speech. Social interactions enhance spontaneous speaking by providing real-world practice. Quantitative results show that students often use active listening ($M = 4.26$, $SD = 0.70$), clarification requests ($M = 4.22$, $SD = 0.72$), and the model of observing fluent speakers ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.81$). Participation in the conversation club was less frequent than that of the learners ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.92$).

In qualitative findings, it is evident that learners gain confidence through peer discussions: “Speaking with different people helps me adapt to accents and speech styles” (Participant 8). These results support Wilschut et al. (2021), who claim that spontaneous speech proficiency is better in interactive learning environments. This study highlights how cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social strategies support spontaneous speech adaptation. Quantitative data illustrate strategy frequency, while qualitative data provide deeper insights into learners’ real-world applications. These findings reinforce the importance of structured cognitive strategies (Choe, 2020), linguistic flexibility (Saito & Plonsky, 2019), psychological resilience (Nissen, 2023), and social interaction (Wilschut et al., 2021). A holistic approach integrating these strategies can enhance fluency and confidence in real-time communication, contributing to more effective spontaneous speech instruction in EFL settings.

6. Conclusion

This research investigated how EFL students deal with spontaneous speaking tasks employing cognitive, linguistic, psychological, and social strategies. The results of the study revealed that cognitive strategies such as mental rehearsal and metacognitive awareness are used in the management of speech production, linguistic strategies including paraphrasing and discourse markers for maintaining fluency, psychological strategies including self-efficacy and anxiety regulation for enhanced confidence, and social strategies including peer learning and interaction with native speakers for the improvement of conversational skills. These results support the previous studies because the participants employed similar strategies in handling the challenges they encountered while speaking. However, the study has some limitations. The study only focused on university students; thus, the findings cannot be compared to those of others. Besides, the long-term effectiveness of these strategies is not known. Future research should extend the investigation to how adaptation strategies change with proficiency levels and how AI-enabled speech technologies can help develop spontaneous speaking skills. From a pedagogical perspective, the findings of this study suggest that EFL programs should include teaching strategies to help students deal with real-time speech production. Teachers should incorporate games such as role play, group work, and relaxation techniques to enhance students’ self-assurance and fluidity. Equally important is the design of assessment rubrics, as Budiharso et al. (2024) demonstrated through the application of Bloom’s taxonomy in evaluating speaking and writing performance. Moreover, teacher education and in-service training should provide teachers with resources to encourage spontaneous speaking. As a result, the presented approaches can improve the quality, precision, and timeliness of the responses given in real-life conversations.

Ethical Issues

The author confirmed that the study does not need approval from the ethics committee according to the research integrity rules in his country. Informed consent was also obtained from each respondent before data collection to ensure respondents' confidentiality and anonymity. Respondents were given complete information regarding the purpose of the research and their right to withdraw from participation at any time without consequences. (Date of Confirmation: 11/11/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The data are not publicly available due to privacy reasons.

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